

ROLE AND INFLUENCE OF SURROGATE MOTHERHOOD CONTRACT IN THE SPHERE OF LAW. (THESIS)

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Today although laws related to the field of family law have been adopted in most of the countries of the world, because of the lack of regulation of surrogate motherhood, we are facing problematic social and legal relations.

The most important issue of society's life is the well-being of the family. The legality of surrogate motherhood contracts is one of the most topical and complex issues in family and civil law. The practice of surrogate motherhood contract is gradually becoming acceptable both theoretically and practically in the USA, Russia, Central Asia and other countries of the world.

Nowadays, as can be seen from the above source, it is becoming urgent to give legal solutions to the issue of surrogate motherhood contract in the legal society of the theoretical and practical aspects. After all, there are enough problematic social and legal relations related to unregulated surrogate motherhood in everyday life.

We know that in the current national legislation, the contract is a legal form that allows for the regulation of various social relations between the parties. The limits of the actions that can be performed, as well as the consequences of non-fulfillment by the parties to the contract, should be indicated in the contract. In practice, today the contract is considered one of the most convenient forms of regulating the behavior of the parties. The main reason for this is that in the legal field, parties can agree on any terms and demand a specially agreed upon result. The legal regulation of contracts manifest in the order of their conclusion and the fulfillment of their obligations by the parties, as well as in the responsibility for non-fulfillment or improper fulfillment of such obligations. Therefore, the legal drafting of the contract to express the rights and obligations of the parties to the surrogate motherhood contract serves as a guarantee of the rights of the parties. To date, the surrogate motherhood contract between a surrogate mother and genetic parents for the birth of a child has not been directly and fully established in civil law. In this regard, the question arises as to which type of civil contract the contract on surrogate motherhood belongs. In

most countries of the world, due to the adoption of laws related to the field of family law, such problematic socio-legal relations are not encountered.

In some foreign countries, based on these features of the contract, a surrogate motherhood contract is concluded.

However, the recognition of the practice of surrogacy and the intense global debate about its ethical, social and economic aspects highlight the legal silence on this issue in most jurisdictions. But the legal silence on this issue does not prevent the implementation of the surrogate motherhood program in practice. On the contrary, surrogate motherhood creates a number of problematic socio-legal relations.

Today, relying on the opinions of foreign scientists, it should be emphasized that the above-mentioned legal silence is a source of uncertainty in some countries, and the practice of surrogate motherhood is one of the last options for becoming parents . There are many moral and legal difficulties that prevent people from living as a healthy family.

As a result, disputes related to these legal difficulties are repeatedly referred to the courts of these countries. However, unfortunately, the courts are not provided with consistent and comprehensive legal documents and measures to successfully resolve conflict situations related to the practice of surrogate motherhood. The process of analysis of existing general jurisdiction laws in foreign experience shows that the most common attitude is a policy of complete disregard for the practice of surrogacy.

With the emergence of a conflicting situation during the surrogacy program, the parties turn to the court authorities in each individual case to ensure the legality of the surrogacy contract and the fulfillment of the terms of the contract by the parties. As a result, the resolution of these disputes is left to the discretion of the judicial authorities.

In our opinion, the main goal of our research on surrogate motherhood is to convey to the scientific community the importance of full recognition of the surrogate motherhood contract, which is currently an urgent social and legal need and has not yet been considered in our legislation.

It should be noted that in order to determine the applicable legal norms, it is necessary to classify the nature of the relations that arise.

A surrogate motherhood contract includes terms that can be regulated by family and civil law. It can be noted that the contract of surrogate motherhood, although it is close to the contract of service in its essence, but due to its nature,

it is independent and is not included in the norms of the Civil Code of Uzbekistan which is an unnamed (untypical) type of contract with character.

In many countries where there is a surrogacy contract, its form is not indicated, because the surrogate motherhood contract is not classified as a separate, independent type of contract. In practice, in our opinion, the conclusion of a surrogate motherhood contract in written form certified by a notary is a reasonable and acceptable solution.

The need to legalize the mandatory written form of the surrogate motherhood contract is evidenced by the fact that the contract acquires both personal and confidential significance. In addition, the surrogate motherhood contract creates additional obligations of the parties within the contract. In our opinion, if the terms of the contract are not confirmed in writing, it is very likely that the parties will face a problem situation due to the lack of agreement on any of the terms orally.

In addition, if the parties do not conclude a notarized written agreement, there is a risk that the parties will not have sufficient information about the scope of the services to be received, their content, etc . In practice, the absence of a written contract on surrogate motherhood affects the scope of services to the parties, their rights and obligations to each other, the terms of termination of the contract, as well as many conditions related to the implementation of various procedures and does not allow the factors to be specified in detail. At this point, in our opinion, the need to present the notarized form of the surrogacy contract to the parties as a solution to the problem is absolutely justified. Another aspect, in our opinion, is that the notarial confirmation of the surrogate motherhood contract provides an opportunity to determine the true will of the parties and increase the strength of the family institution in society.

Thus, identifying the parties to this agreement is a key step in the surrogate motherhood contract. First of all, it should be noted that there are two views on this matter.

According to the first theory , two parties participate in the surrogate motherhood contract. Since the surrogate motherhood contract is similar to the fee-for-service contract in many respects, the surrogate mother is appointed as the executor of the contract, and the genetic parent is the customer or customer of the services. According to another theory, in addition to the surrogate mother and genetic parents, the surrogate motherhood contract also includes a third party - a medical organization. According to experts, without the participation of the medical organization, the obligations of the parties under the contract on

surrogate motherhood cannot be properly fulfilled. Because, within the framework of the surrogate motherhood program, the need and obligation to conduct a medical examination of the parties, as well as the fact that the introduction of assisted reproductive technologies should be carried out and legally strengthened in a specialized medical organization.

Many experts in this field strongly recommend concluding a bilateral surrogate motherhood contract between the surrogate mother and the genetic parents. They believe that a successful surrogacy course, the outcome of the surrogacy program depends mainly on a quality and qualified surrogate motherhood contract. In this matter, in our opinion, the more complete all the details of the contract are, the less likely the parties will abuse their rights. In addition, the procedure for the use of assisted reproductive technologies, the prohibition of their use and the limitation of their use, spouses and surrogate mothers have been informed in writing, and their acceptance of these conditions means their consent to participate in the surrogacy program.

From this we can conclude that the first step in concluding a surrogate motherhood contract is to inform the parties of their full rights and obligations in the appropriate manner. In the next stages, the parties will sign the various protocols provided by the legal documents and provided by the above-mentioned medical organization, undergo medical examination by surrogate mothers and future parents, and give consent to the next stage. After that, as with the conclusion of any other civil legal contract, the parties must agree and sign the terms of the surrogate motherhood contract, as well as fulfill all their obligations under this contract in the appropriate manner.

Today there is no consensus on the legal formalization of relations for the implementation of the program. Some believe that it is necessary to conclude a tripartite agreement between genetic parents, a surrogate mother and a medical institution and it is advisable to develop standard forms.

In conclusion, the following arguments should be noted:

First, because there are no legal requirements for surrogate motherhood contracts, many abuses are committed by both surrogate mothers and genetic parents. In this regard, it is important to clearly regulate the rights and obligations of the parties to the surrogacy contract, as well as issues of liability for non-compliance.

Secondly, since the surrogacy program is associated with many natural risks, it is necessary to protect the legally guaranteed rights of the contract parties in the surrogate motherhood contract.

Thirdly, in our opinion, the surrogate motherhood contract is aimed at legal protection of the unborn child, which is the most important condition and product of the implementation of the surrogate motherhood program.

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